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ASSESSMENT OF THE PHENOMENON OF POLITICAL ABSENTEEISM AND METHODS OF COUNTERACTING ELECTORAL NON-PARTICIPATION

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Abstract

The phenomenon of absenteeism, in other words, electoral non-participation, does not have a unanimous assessment within the scientific community and ranges from an extremely negative interpretation as a threat to representative democracy to positive connotations as an indicator of the transformation of the political system. The purpose of this article is to explore the spectrum of interpretations of this issue, as well as to analyze the proposed methods of counteracting/combating electoral non-participation.

Keywords: absenteeism, electoral non-participation, political system, sanctions, motivation.

Absenteeism is an inherent phenomenon of the electoral process. In our opinion, it is not entirely correct to talk about this phenomenon in a positive or negative context. This element has always existed, exists, and will exist as long as elections are held, and this fact should be taken for granted. We should not deny, ignore or try to eradicate it, but understand the nature, causes and components of electoral non-participation in order to work with it in the future. In addition, it is necessary to try to assess absenteeism based on existing theory and practice. A number of scholars from the post-Soviet space argue that voter abstention is an exclusively negative phenomenon that needs to be addressed. Scholars are convinced that low voter turnout is a direct threat to representative democracy, the legitimacy of government, and other negative trends. Moreover, in the literature, we have often encountered the shifting of responsibility to unaware citizens who are apathetic, uninterested, irresponsible, infantile, disappointed, and therefore do not participate in the electoral process.

We do not share this vision and offer our own view of absenteeism. First of all, it should be noted that a number of citizens do not vote because they do not have basic skills of political choice, have a low level of political/electoral culture, do not realize the importance of the institution of elections and the act of expressing their will, and naively believe that by abstaining or ignoring they can demonstrate protest, dissatisfaction or disappointment (as discussed above). It should be noted at the outset that we believe that the behavior of absentees is destructive, because it is much more effective to express your position with a voice, and non-participation does not absolve you from responsibility. The problem of absenteeism is not only about citizens; on the contrary, we should focus on the political and party system, the level of democracy and corruption, political ideology, media freedom, trust in public authorities, government legitimacy, etc. The higher the level of political culture of citizens and the development of the political system (we mean the number of political parties,

their competition, political alternatives and real choices, program statements, the level of populism, ideological divide, fragmentation of parties, awareness and education campaigns, the presence and development of civil society, etc.), the higher the turnout in elections. This also implies the methods of increasing voter turnout. In our opinion, resorting to fines and other sanctions and coercive measures is a deliberately wrong decision, a so-called "one-time action", since such means will not lead to systemic qualitative changes. There is a high probability that citizens will vote for the suspended sentence under duress, primarily in order to avoid receiving a fine. Although practice proves positive quantitative results of a mandatory vote backed by sanctions, what about qualitative characteristics and the principle of voluntary expression of will? These means are unlikely to increase the level of political culture of citizens and the electorate's awareness of the political system, candidates, program statements, etc. In addition, voters can deliberately spoil ballots or vote against all candidates, and in this case, technically, they will not be considered as evaders, but what is the value of such a vote? [5]

The next group of absentees is satisfied with the current state of affairs. There is a certain number of citizens who are satisfied with the current government, their decisions and actions at the time of the election. They believe that the state and they personally do not need any changes, and therefore it is inappropriate to vote, wasting their resources. The question arises as to how and whether such voters should be motivated to vote, and how acceptable it is to apply sanctions or other mobilization efforts to such a group of voters.

Another group of voter avoidance relates to elections in authoritarian states. Obviously, elections are a defining element of democracies, but we do not live in an illusory world and recognize that elections are currently held in various political regimes with varying degrees of success. In most of these countries, there are no alternatives, and the turnout rate is through the roof.

However, the number of citizens who did not vote is guided, among other things, by the motive of not supporting the government. In order not to be opportunists of the regime, citizens make a conscious decision not to vote, not to support, not to be involved. How to treat this group of citizens, whether they need to be additionally “motivated” and by what methods?

Moreover, returning to the theory of elites, it is useful to note that not all citizens participate in voting. Apologists of this concept focus on the fact that the part of citizens who are unconscious, irresponsible, uneducated, ignoring the electoral process, only improve it by their non-participation, as they leave the choice to the “best”. Some supporters of the theory point out that widespread participation of the masses has brought numerous tyrants and dictators to power, and therefore limited participation is necessary for the benefit of the citizens themselves [1].

It is worth briefly describing the methods of increasing electoral participation and engaging citizens in political processes. Among other things, the use of a turnout threshold attracts attention. Practical application shows positive results in increasing voter turnout, but it is worth asking the question of the feasibility of this tool. Let’s model a situation where the electoral threshold in country A at the national presidential election is set at 50% +1. During the first round of voting, 49% of citizens came to the polls, and therefore, according to the current legislation, the election is recognized as not having taken place. The next stage of the election, which requires additional resources from both sides, let’s say, achieved the desired turnout of 51%, but did the participation of an additional 2% of citizens affect the alignment of political forces? How much of a critical mass is 2% and how representative are they? Another question is whether the turnout threshold can be considered a liberal means to attract more citizens, given the principle of voluntary participation [2].

The next tool that we have found in the literature, in particular, in the dissertation of Ukrainian scholar D. Gavryliuk, is the formation of so-called lists of unreliable voters. Theoretically, this seems possible and will probably influence moral judgment, etc., but how can it be implemented in practice? Is it about creating boards with photos and names of evaders, or about using social networks to shame dishonest citizens? We believe that such a measure is somewhat ridiculous, difficult to apply in practice, and unlikely to be effective in combating electoral disenfranchisement. Moreover, the methods of implementation remain vague and create more questions than answers [3].

We have already mentioned the use of fines and other sanctioning methods above, so we would only like to emphasize that such things are undemocratic and violate the rights of citizens. In the literature and in practice, there is a method of imposing prison terms, imprisonment, and criminal liability, but we are equally convinced that this is a violation of basic rights and freedoms, non-compliance with not only national legislation but also international conventions, encroachment on the constitutional rights of citizens, etc. This practice should not take place in the electoral process [3; 6].

There are proposals to impose “professional sanctions” on abstainers, namely, banning them from public office for a certain period of time. Again, this contradicts the constitutional right to work, but for Ukraine, it could be an acceptable practice, since a civil servant who does not realize the importance of voting and the value of his/her own vote is likely to be ineffective in his/her position (especially when it comes to expressing the will of the people, elected positions).

The effectiveness of the mandatory vote, which is not backed up by sanctions, has shown to have little impact in practice. In addition, compulsory voting and higher turnout can only mask the problem, imitate the presence of an active voter, and artificially inflate participation rates. The opposite trend to mandatory voting is the use of optional voting (for the elderly, for example). Thus, we will get an automatic increase in turnout if we exclude elderly citizens from the ratio (denominator) or add their percentage to both the numerator and denominator in the case of voting.

The next method of combating absenteeism is the development and use of alternative voting methods along with advances in information and communication technologies. This is one of the determining factors in increasing voter participation. Indeed, voting by mail, absentee ballots, at home (remotely outside polling stations), via an app or the Internet, etc. reduce potential costs for voters and therefore encourage participation [4].

Another option to combat absenteeism is to block cards and freeze bank accounts. The solution may be very original, but let’s project the results of applying such a mechanism to the abstainers of the electoral process. First of all, everything that concerns financial, economic, and material restrictions of citizens and the creation of additional burdens for the population causes fierce resistance, conflicts, and rejection. Such actions are extremely sensitive for the population, perhaps even more so than the alternative of imprisonment. In addition, it will in no way lead to positive results. Obviously, our life is built on monetary exchange, and therefore citizens will try to find any possible ways out and bypass this decision. Such a decision threatens the flourishing of the “black market” and the “shadow economy”; it will impose additional burdens on the judicial and economic systems, the state budget; it will create problems with utility bills, loan repayments, and salaries; even paying fines for evasion will be problematic or even impossible. This is a completely unjustified step that will only lead to high social tension [7].

The real possible means of increasing citizens’ motivation to participate is positive systemic actions by the authorities that improve the political environment, raise political awareness and work proactively with the additional use of alternative voting methods and ICT. Sporadic attempts to motivate the electorate twice every five years (even with the help of sanctions) will not lead to a qualitative improvement of the electoral process. Bilateral interaction between the state and the citizen is a kind of key to increasing voter turnout. The national aspect is also worth mentioning: Ukraine gained its independence in 1991, so our electoral cul-

ture is still being formed. Of course, we have had elements of electability since the Cossacks, but systemic alternative democratic elections became a reality only 33 years ago. In addition, Ukraine does not stand out from the global trend. Yes, it is negative, because the turnout is steadily decreasing in different countries, but we are not an anomaly. The crisis of the electoral institution is observed in various countries, and therefore we are within the norm. Another issue is that the level of turnout in “transitional democracies” indicates political transformations and the readiness of the whole society to change.

Thus, the conclusion is that the naturalness of the phenomenon of absenteeism does not require categorical methods of struggle, but rather ways to understand its awareness and origin. It is an integral element of elections, just like the election campaign, the electoral system, electoral legislation, etc.

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